

MAKSUD SHEIKHZADE'S LOVE FOR THE MOTHERLAND

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Annotation. *The article talks about the life and work of Maksud Sheikhzade, the son of the Azerbaijan people, who called the Uzbek land his motherland. In his poetry collections and works, including the poem 'Tashkentnoma', it is stated that the works of the heart spoken to the honor of the Homeland, Motherland and people are reflected.*

Key words: *poetry, Tashkentnoma, poem, poet, teacher, literature, classical, history.*

Maqsud Sheikhzadeh was born in 1908 in the village of Aktash, Azerbaijan, in the family of doctor Ma'sumbek, a leading intellectual of his time. Interest in literature, love for poetry appeared in the poet's heart and mind in this family and remained in harmony until the last day of his life.

The great thirst for knowledge and study motivates the young poet to read and learn. Maqsud Sheikhzade, who knows the Russian language well, gets acquainted with rare works of Russian classical and Western literature, and begins to deeply study Azerbaijani folk art and classical literature. He tries to transfer this knowledge, this love for literature to the students of Darbana in Dagestan, and later Buynoksk.

In 1928, Maqsud Shaykhzade moved to Tashkent, and from this year, his whole life, destiny, and creativity were inextricably linked with Uzbekistan, which he called his motherland.

First of all, he is a teacher, then he works in the editorial offices of our republic's newspapers and magazines, and he is always in the hot life and praises it. The words of the poet's heart in honor of the Motherland, the motherland, and the people make up dozens of poetic collections.

Our beloved poet translated the rarest works of Russian classical and Soviet literature, the best examples of the literature of the brotherly nations, and presented the most unique and royal works of world classical literature to Uzbek readers.

When we read the poet's poetic works, we fully believe that their author is a scientist. This is especially noticeable when seeing the world, perceiving, reviving the pages of history. We cannot imagine the philosophical depth and intellectual depth of Uzbek poetry without the work of Shaikhzade.

The leading feature of Sheikhzade's dramaturgy was the reference to history, the illumination of history, which we can also see in his poetry. Interest in history is characteristic of his early poems, poems, and political lyrics. The poet compares his time with the past, praises the new time, expresses his love and pride.

This principle is especially evident in the poet's poem "Tashkentnoma".

A memento that everyone had put in their city:

Or a tree, or a child, a bridge, or a verse.

Either song or medicine, school, seizures,

Summary: Any good in the world...

Original text: Xar kim o'z shaharida qo'ygan estalik:

Yo daraxt, yo farzand, ko'prik, yo misra.

Yo qushiq, yo dori, maktab, soqchilik,
Xulosa: dunyoda biron yaxshilik...

He wrote an epic about Tashkent and the people of Tashkent, leaving a memory of his age in the memory of Sheikhzadeh and the Uzbek people. The epic consists of 18 chapters. There is no description of everything in this epic, as it is in other epics of the poet. Some episodes described in one chapter are logically connected to each other by a significant idea. We see this situation in Mirtemir's poem "Surat", V. Mayakovsky, A. Tvardovsky. N. In some of Gribachev's epics, Shaikhzade unites some episodes and scenes through an important idea or the image of a lyrical hero.

"Tashkentnoma" is a lyrical-philosophical poem. His hero is Tashkent, the people of Tashkent and a poet.

Each chapter of the epic revives some page of the history of Tashkent. Tashkent's "thousands of years old story", about the people's lack of rights, people's toils, "stones used to tell, it entered the language!"

But even though the people lived under the shackles of slavery for thousands of years, they created a wonderful culture and preserved their national pride and dignity.

The rebellious spirit of Tashkent
It shined in the sixteenth year,
The seed of will fell to the ground,
The gardener who planted the seed was the people.

Original text:

Toshkentlikning isyonkor ruhi
O'n oltinchi yilida balqidi,
Erga tushdi erkning urugi,
Urug' ekkkan bog'bon xalq edi.

The poet's epic describes the joining of Uzbekistan to Russia in vivid scenes, and poetically describes the friendship of the Russian and Uzbek peoples.

But when the artist turns to ancient history, he does not do it only for the sake of history. Comparing today's happy days with history, he once again emphasizes the image of Tashkent and the greatness of the victories achieved.

In the poem, the poet describes today's beauty of Tashkent in realistic pictures. City streets, avenues, squares, theaters, Tashkent residents passing through these streets and squares are embodied before our eyes.

While narrating the life of Tashkent, the poet is very happy that he is from Tashkent, he talks about his friends and acquaintances with pride and joy.

Once upon a time I praised my city to you
As you describe, you pause for a moment,
"Are there so many?" you suspected it
"We'll tell when we see!" you gestured.
And you said - after seeing it:
" you have little praise, excellent house!"
dress to be suit figure,
In the heart amour to my country, sincerity.
I wanted it to be poured into the epic,
Sorry for writing late, friend!

Those who stand here, or who see,
Or those who want to see,
Or those who asked the shape of my Tashkent,
Those who carry the pattern on their tongues...
This song is for you - my song is sweet,
Prose is a heavy step, verse is a slow step.

Original text:

Bir vaqtlar men senga shahrimni maqtov
Qilarkan tarifin, sen bir oz to'xtab,
«Shunchalar bormikan?» deb gumon qilding,
«Qo'raganda aytamiz!» deb imo qilding.
Va aytding – darvoke ko'rgandan keyin:
«Maqtoving oz ekan, soz ekan uying!»
Qomatga munosib bo'lsin deb kiyim,
Shaxrimga dildagi yuk, ixlos
Dostonga quyilsin degandim u cho'k,
Kechikib yozganim kechirgin, o'rtoq!
Bu yerda turganlar, yoki ko'rganlar,
Yoki qarab, deb istab turganlar
Yoki Toshkentimning shaklin so'rganlar,
Naqshini qalbida olib yurganlar...
sizga bu taronam — kuyim armugon,
Nasr — og'ir qadam, nazm — chopon

The poem is rich in deep philosophical generalizations. Especially, the poet's heartfelt words dedicated to the Motherland in the last chapter excite the reader and constitute the main pathos of the poem.

Sheikhzaden's epic "Tashkentnoma" is one of the epics created in Uzbek poetry in the last years after the war, which was greeted with great interest and goodwill by readers.

At a time when the artist's creativity was flourishing, a cruel death brought dust to the life of such a talented artist. February 19, 1967 was a great loss for our literature, art, and science. M. Sheikhzade lived a very blessed life and brought great benefit to his people.

Our nation is rightfully proud of Maksud Shaykhzada, the son of the people of Azerbaijan, but the person who called the Uzbek land his motherland, who dedicated his whole body to it, the artist who rendered service. Poet, dramatist, scientist - these three sides of great talent were embodied in one life.

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